

Performance evaluation of surfactant removal by adsorption technique and its comparative studies with other existing treatment processes : A short review[†]

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Abstract : Adsorption process has been found to be one of the oldest and finest treatment methods for surfactants removal. As the control of water pollution has become important in current years, the use of physical, chemical and biological treatment methods such as membrane filtration, ion-exchange, coagulation/flocculation and biological degradation have become more and more challenging in terms of cost and efficiency. Adsorption is a technique, which is extensively used for surfactant removal. In the present review, the focus is made on the adsorption process using low-cost materials, and it is compared with other techniques for surfactant remediation.

Keywords : Surfactant, adsorption, removal, activated carbon.

Introduction

Surfactant is defined as the surface-active substances that can reduce the surface tension of water significantly. This molecule is made up of a water-soluble (hydrophilic) and a water-insoluble (hydrophobic) component. Due to this structure, the surfactant molecules are aligning themselves to form micelles, which have the capability to separate dirt and oily stains. The surfactants are classified into four groups (Fig. 1) according to their ionic properties produced by the molecular chain : anionic, cationic, non-ionic and Zwitterionic. Among them, ionic surfactants possess nearly two-thirds of all the surfactants while an-

ionic constitute more than 90 percent of the ionic surfactants alone¹. Surfactants are not only used for the production of soap, shampoo, toothpaste and detergents in daily life; they are also extensively applied in industrial processes such as textiles, fibers, food, polymers, cosmetics, paints, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, mining and paper industries^{2,3}. These applications of the surfactants may increase its concentrations in wastewater, produce foam, and penetrate into the underground water bodies, and finally cause hazards. They may also cause dermatitis (i.e. skin infection) for human beings, and act harmful to the aquatic flora and fauna^{4,5}. Due to the above-mentioned

Fig. 1. Classification of surfactants.

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

reasons, various environmental and public health regulatory agencies have restricted limits for anionic surfactants up to 0.5 mg/L for drinking water and relaxable up to 1.0 mg/L for other applications⁶.

Among several treatment methods, adsorption technology is one of the effective techniques that have been successfully employed for surfactant removal from wastewater⁷. There are currently numerous treatment processes available for surfactant removal from aqueous solution. These methods include chemical and electrochemical oxidation^{8,9}, membrane technology¹⁰, coagulation-flocculation^{11,12}, photocatalytic degradation^{13,14}, foam separation¹⁵, adsorption¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and many biological methods¹⁹⁻²¹. The major aim of this article is to compile the recent information regarding the adsorption phenomena for removal of surfactants. For this, an extensive list of sorbent literature on surfactants has been compiled.

Treatment technologies for surfactant removal involving physical and/or chemical and biological processes

The conventional methods for the treatment of surfactant bearing wastewater include physical, chemical and biological treatments. However, these technologies have definite merits and demerits. Many of these processes are not suitable for application on large scale. Some of them involve high cost and some produce huge amount of sludge.

Physical methods : Physical treatment includes membrane filtration process, electrocatalytic degradation and adsorption techniques. The major drawback in membrane filtration is the limited life span before the membrane fouling occurs. As a result, the cost of periodic replacement must be incorporated during the analysis of their economic feasibility. Among all the physical methods, adsorption process has been reported to be the most effective method for wastewater decontamination. Adsorption is acknowledged as a promising practice, because of ease of its operation and comparatively lower cost involved in the treatment process. Moreover, it can be extended to continuous flow mode through column operation. Thus proper designing, fabrication and optimization of the column may produce a high quality effluent.

Commercially available activated carbon is recognized as an efficient adsorbent material in the remediation of surfactant bearing wastewater. Activated carbon possesses useful physical and chemical properties such as high spe-

cific surface areas, wide pore size distributions (including micropores and mesopores), hydrophobic surfaces, and variable surface functional groups. Each property supports the application of activated carbon as an adsorbent for surfactant removal^{18,22,23}. Nevertheless, activated carbon is an expensive adsorbent due to its high cost of manufacturing and poor regeneration ability²⁴. Thus, the use of activated carbon is restricted on these days. As a consequence, for the purpose of removing detergent compounds from contaminated wastewater at a cheap rate, much attention has been paid on various low-cost adsorbents, agricultural by-products, and construction waste materials such as alumina⁷, sand²⁵, sludge²⁶, sediment²⁷, zeolites²⁸, bentonite²⁹, rice husk³⁰, waste tyre rubber³¹, soil^{32,33}, rocks³⁴, etc. As a challenge, to build up cheaper and effective adsorbents, many non-conventional low-cost adsorbents such as clay materials, agricultural wastes and industrial waste products have also been suggested^{35,36}.

Chemical treatments : The major process involved in chemical treatment of surfactant wastewater is coagulation/flocculation^{8,11}. It involves the addition of substances such as Ca^{2+} , Al^{3+} , or Fe^{3+} salts into the effluent, to bring about the coagulation. Furthermore, the use of cationic polyelectrolytes appeared to be effective for the coagulation of anionic surfactants³⁷. According to Lin *et al.*³⁸, the surfactant removal from wastewater could be enhanced by employing two-stage coagulation, preceded by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide. Generally, chemical methods are less economical but more efficient. The major disadvantage is that, sometimes the chemicals are too expensive, and the price fluctuates. For this process, chemical treatments of the sludge (or floc) at the end of the treatment process is also necessary.

Biological methods : Biological treatment of wastewater is an economical method alternative to physical and chemical method. In such processes adsorption by microbial biomass (living or dead) and microbial degradation are commonly used in the treatment of surfactant containing effluents^{26,39-41}. Dhoub *et al.*²¹ have elucidated that the treatment of surfactant containing effluents using biological processes such as activated sludge is problematic due to the slow kinetics of degradation and due to foam production. In recent years, constructed wetlands were recognized to be effective for surfactant remediation^{42,43}. But the major drawback is that, it requires substantial

land area and is constrained by sensitivity toward diurnal variation as well as toxicity of chemicals. However, no method has yet demonstrated the complete removal of surfactants. There is still a need to find cost-effective methods that can be applied in treatment plants. Table 1 shows the advantages and disadvantages of some selected physical, chemical and biological treatment methods used for surfactants removal.

Adsorption – an effective process for surfactant remediation

Surfactant adsorption to solid-liquid interfaces is a process where transfer of surfactant molecules from bulk solution phase to the solid-liquid interface takes place. This partitioning of the adsorbate species between the interface and the bulk is possible, if the interface is energetically favoured by the surfactant compared to bulk solution^{44,45}.

Table 1. Existing and promising processes for surfactant removal

Methods	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Ref.
Electrochemical oxidation	Galvanostatic electrolysis using Ti–Ru–Sn ternary oxide and boron-doped diamond (BDD) anode	Faster sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) mineralisation and chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal was achieved by chlorine mediated oxidation at Ti–Ru–SnO ₂ anode	High cost of electricity	9
Coagulation-flocculation	Jar-test using coagulant FeCl ₃	Effective in the reduction of anionic surfactants (99%) and COD (88%)	pH dependent between 7 and 9. Huge floc generation	11
Activated carbon	Surfactant removal by adsorption technique	Effective removal of a wide variety of surfactants	Regeneration difficulties	16, 18
Ion-exchange and membrane separation	MIEX [®] is used as ion-exchange resin. More effective, when coupled with membrane process “ultra filtration”	Regeneration ability. No adsorbent loss	The phenomena are more pronounced for the surfactant concentration below the critical micelle concentration (CMC) values. Concentrated sludge production. Not effective for all types of surfactants	10
Foam separation	Cationic surfactant (cetylpyridinium chloride, CPC) and an anionic surfactant (sodium dodecylsulfate, SDS) from water by multistage foam fractionation in a bubble-cap trayed column was employed	Simultaneous removal of both anionic and cationic surfactant. Removal efficacy increases with increasing foam height per tray, feed liquid flow rate, feed surfactant concentration, and number of stages. It shows negative feedback on increasing air flow rate	Economically not feasible.	15
Biological degradation	Degradation of anionic surfactant sodium lauryl ether sulfate (SLES) was carried out by a conventional enrichment-culture technique using <i>Citrobacter braakii</i>	The process was improved (i.e. degradation from 0.065 to 0.15 g/L/h) to reduce the hydraulic retention time (HRT) from 20 to 5 h; when the bioreactor is coupled with mineral microfiltration membrane	Skilled supervision required. Not adaptable in middle-class households	21
Constructed wetlands	Removal of anionic surfactants using constructed wetland with horizontal subsurface flow. Rhizosphere aeration via the vegetation roots strongly supported the removal efficacy	More than 50% of the anionic surfactants are degraded initially	Dependent on climate conditions. Huge land area required for implementation	42

In the solid surfaces, adsorption of surfactant as monomers may occur at low surfactant concentrations. However, with an increase in surfactant concentrations, in certain cases, surfactant monomers adsorbed to solid surfaces initiate to aggregate and form micelle-like structures (i.e. bilayers) called 'admicelles'⁴⁵. Subsequently, adsorption of additional surfactant may quickly increase until the formation of a complete bilayer of surfactant on the solid surface takes place. These surface aggregates are formed beyond a critical concentration below the critical micelle concentration (CMC) values, and is acknowledged as critical hemimicellar concentration (HMC). The phenomena are referred as hemimicellization⁴⁶.

Zhang and Somasundaran⁴⁵ have reported that three types of interactions are possible in the surfactant adsorption at solid-liquid interface. The attractive or repulsive interaction between the hydrophilic group and the surface, the attractive interaction between the hydrophobic group and the surface, and the lateral interactions that occur between adsorbed surfactants. This primarily depends on the nature of the surfactants as well as solid

surfaces. Among them, the electrostatic interactions between the hydrophilic group and the surface, and the hydrogen bonding are more pronounced^{44,45}. In case of ionic surfactants, if the surfactant and adsorbent surfaces are oppositely charged, the adsorption kinetics is very fast. On the other hand, if surfactant and the adsorbent possess similar charge, repulsion takes place causing insignificant adsorption.

The adsorption isotherm of an ionic surfactant on an oppositely charged surface was described as "Somasundaran-Fuerstenau" type and it is very characteristic. The isotherm can be subdivided into four regions (Fig. 2)⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. Region I adsorption follows Henry's law, i.e. adsorption increases linearly with concentration. Here the surfactants are adsorbed as monomers and do not interact with each other. The adsorption phenomena are primarily based on electrostatic forces. Region II shows a sudden increase in adsorption. This is due to the formation of surface aggregate of the surfactant molecules on the solid surface. Region III shows a slower rate of increase in adsorption compared to region II. Here, the solid

Fig. 2. Characteristic isotherm curve for adsorption of ionic surfactant⁴⁷.

surface is electrically neutralized by the adsorbed surfactant ions, and the electrostatic attraction is no longer operative and adsorption takes place due to lateral attraction alone with a reduced slope. Region IV is the plateau region above the CMC. If the surfactant concentration reaches CMC, the surfactant monomer activity becomes constant and any further increase in concentration contributes only to the micellization in solution and it does not change the adsorption density. The adsorption in this region is mainly through lateral hydrophobic interaction between the hydrocarbon chains. This type of interaction leads to enhanced surfactant removal from the environment. Thus properly chosen solid surface and experimental condition can be utilized for the treatment of surfactant bearing wastewater^{7,47,49}.

On the other hand, in case of non-ionic surfactants, mostly physical adsorption takes place rather than chemisorption or ionic adsorption.

Conclusion

Based on the literature reviewed so far, it is evident that, there has been an increase in utilization of surfactants, resulting in an increase in serious environmental pollution. Various techniques have been utilized for the removal of different types of surfactants. However, practically a successful methodology for the removal of all types of surfactants at low cost has not been established. The above mentioned literatures employed during the researches lead to a conclusion that for removal of surfactants using effective adsorbent materials yields rewarding consequences. It can be concluded that surfactant removal can be achieved up to definite extent by adsorption phenomena which are currently under use.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to IIT Kharagpur for providing the financial assistance.

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